

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PHYSICS**Yusupova Madinabonu A'zamjan kizi****Andijan State Pedagogical Institute****Assistant of the Department of Sciences of physics and technology**

Annotation: in the article, the process of learning is the systematic development of spiritual and mental abilities, while the process of learning is a holistic lesson, which relies on various methods(methods). Methods of using modern technologies in teaching physics. To learn to use them in lecture, practical and laboratory classes. Interesting and effective conduct of physics lessons, transparent assessment methods are presented.

Keywords: methodology, educational training, assessment, mystery assessment, exemplary, Millionaire game, reflection.

In my experience, he is a determined businessman,
a man alert, brave and ambitious
from a thousand idle people
is better.

Amir Temur.

In fact, the fact that such words were quoted by the great general Amir Temur in his work "Temur tuzuklari" is of great spiritual and educational significance today. It should be clear to all of us that where indifference reigns, when the most urgent issues are left to be, education becomes the weakest and weakest point. My goal is to further increase the will of the cadets during training. After all, a strong-willed person believes in himself and is not afraid to take on any difficult task. [1]

It is known that the process of education is the process of systematic development of spiritual and mental abilities, formation of knowledge and concepts, and the ability to use the acquired knowledge. This process can be

carried out by the learner himself or with the help of another teacher. The educational process takes place based on various methods (methods).[4] In the continuing education system, in accordance with the state order and social demand, each educational institution and the pedagogues serving in it are responsible for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, creatively by introducing the latest achievements of science into practice. To educate a socially active, highly moral, professional, loyal to the country, educated in the spirit of national and universal human values, able to think creatively and independently, feel his duty and responsibility before the state, society and family, competitive and well-rounded person and implementation of important tasks such as bringing to maturity, instilling the idea of national independence in their minds and hearts. The successful solution of this task is inextricably linked with the use of modern educational technologies in the educational process. The introduction of modern pedagogical technology into educational processes requires, first of all, the humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations. Any pedagogical technology used without establishing such a relationship will not give the expected effect. Pedagogical technology based on the humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations is opposed to authoritarian technology, in which educational activities consisting of cooperation, care, respect for the personality of the learner are organized. The humanized attitude of the teacher to the personality of the pupil or student is carried out at the expense of love for children, concern for their fate, high trust in the individual, mutual cooperation, perfect communication culture, voluntariness and freedom, encouragement and resistance to shortcomings. increases. Achieving the intended goal requires the activeness and equal rights of all participants in the educational process. Democratization of the educational process leads to the equalization of civil rights of teachers and students, the creation of conditions for students to choose and freely express their opinions and views. This also complies with the norms

guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The peculiarity of the new relationship is that it is different from the traditional education, directing students to the set goal without prohibiting their independence and creative learning activities, organizing learning activities in cooperation, taking into account their interest and needs. and is characterized by the fact that it is carried out due to free and active work. The new pedagogical relations that have arisen in the process of education require the use of modern pedagogical technologies in this process. For this, special means of introducing pedagogical technologies will be necessary. [3]

For example, every student should know the criteria for evaluating and motivating students' knowledge in the class of solving problems in physics. During the whole lesson, active students work on all the given problems correctly and quickly. On the other hand, slow-learning cadets can do one or two problems correctly, and they want to get an exemplary grade for these correctly worked problems. At this time, the teacher finds it difficult to assess the students' knowledge. Because these students have worked the problem correctly even if they have worked on a few problems. By using the following method, it is possible to eliminate this problem and increase students' interest in the lesson. The teacher announces the topic of the practical lesson. The lecture will be reinforced. "Millionaires Game" method is used to check the knowledge of students. In this method, the teacher prepares Blitz questions based on the given lecture. The questions are read by the teacher. The student who answered each question will be given a card with "200,000 soums" written on it. After the questions are finished, the number of collected cards is determined. Any cadet who collects 5 cards will collect 1 million and is encouraged as a "group millionaire", that is, a spiritually rich person, a person with strong human capital. If there are students who have collected more than 5 cards, they are considered "supper millionaires". Problems will be worked out in order to create practical skills based on the theoretical

knowledge of the subject.

We use the "Mystery assessment" method in order to develop comprehensibility, speed, initiative in solving problems related to the topic, and to arouse students' interest in solving problems. This method is organized as follows. It provides detailed information about the required physical quantities and their expressions. After that, the problem solving begins. The condition of problem 1 is announced. The teacher marks the first three students who worked the problem correctly and quickly with the letter "N" instead of a grade. Then they start working on problem 2. The first three students who worked correctly and quickly for this problem will mark the letter "A" in their notebook. For problem 3, the letter "M" is not, etc. In this way, the following issues are dealt with. If one student correctly and quickly solves all the problems given during the lesson (8 problems in this exercise), instead of a consecutive score, letters forming the word "EXEMPLARY" will be placed. At the end of the lesson, students who have collected all the letters of the word "EXEMPLARY" (at least 7) will be given an incentive card written "Exemplary Student of Physics" and rated with a grade of "5". During the lesson, students who can collect the letters "SAMPLE" will be given a "Good Participant in Physics" card and will be graded "4". "Physics is an interesting science." Work on yourself." A card will be issued and these students will be graded "3". Using this method, the following results can be achieved:

1. Students are interested in collecting mysterious letters, they try to solve the problem faster, they are interested in the results of their work.
2. Even a student who received a grade of "3" is not dissatisfied with this grade, on the contrary, he understands why he got a low grade and starts working on himself.[6]

I believe that it is very important to use reflection at the end of every lecture, practical, laboratory and seminar lesson. It means reflection. There are many types of reflection. this method does not require a lot of time, but reflecting

the entire lesson, the subject is strengthened in the student. For example, reflection "3.4.5.6.7" in which the student should write 3-letter, 4-letter, 5-letter, 6-letter and 7-letter words from the science words used during the lesson. The teacher will give one or two minutes for this. For example, if the topic of electric current is covered, they write such words as 3-current, 4-current, 5-particle, 6-charge, 7-carrier(3-tok, 4-oqim, 5-zarra, 6-zaryad, 7-tashuvchi). When the teacher gives, the student starts flipping through the notebook, remembers all the information that has been passed, discussed, discussed, and here the brain attack begins. When the time is up, whoever wants to read the 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 letter words written by the students, but all the students write. And they can analyze today's lesson. He reviews what words we used in today's lesson, what word he remembered today, what word he missed today, and what words he used while writing. When each student reads, other students say yes, I forgot that, wow, my teacher said that too, it helps him to strengthen and reflect on the topic he has studied. If we use this method at the beginning of the lesson, it can be a basis for strengthening the topic learned yesterday.

What the teacher achieves through this method: we can organize the process through an interesting situation for them to repeat and reinforce yesterday's lesson; moreover, they should remember the important words that they did not pay attention to in yesterday's lesson and write them down in the notebook today; and at the same time, it greatly helps to develop the skill of writing words correctly.[5]

Our main task is to provide young people with the necessary professional knowledge in their fields, and to train them to become perfect people who will ensure the great future of our Motherland by providing them with dedication to their profession and all-round human education. I believe that every physics teacher can achieve this task only if he uses modern, advanced methods of teaching with a creative approach rather than traditional methods.

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